

SCREENING OF CASHEW GERMPASMS AGAINST MAJOR PESTS TEA MOSQUITO BUG, *Helopetis Antonii* SIGNORET INFESTATION.

Makawana A.I., Patel H.F., Gaikwad S.S., Bhandari A.J., Patel N.B., Parmar S.G. Damasia D.M.

Horticulture Polytechnic,

Navsari Agricultural University, Paria, Gujarat

aimakawana@nau.in

MS Received: 15.11.2024; MS Revised:28.12.2024; MS Accepted:29.12.2024

MS 3333

(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE)

Abstract

Cashew, (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) is an important profitable nut crop of India. The nuts, apple and other derivatives of this crop are of commercial importance. Among the biotic factors, tea mosquito bug alone has a potential to cause 40 to 50 per cent yield loss in cashew. The average of shoot and panicle damage scale of tea mosquito bug (Table 1) was in the range of 0.44 to 1.09 in different varieties. Vengurla-2 recorded lowest shoot damage scale (0.44) followed by Vengurla-1 (0.48), Vengurla-6 (0.60), Vengurla-7(0.62), Vengurla-5 (0.85) and Vengurla-4 (0.88). While, Vengurla-3 recorded highest shoot damage scale (1.09). While, Vengurla-3 recorded highest average damage scale (1.09). Based on mean damage scales to shoots and panicles due to tea mosquito bug, varieties Vengurla-2, Vengurla-1, Vengurla-6, Vengurla-7, Vengurla-5 and Vengurla-4 found less susceptible

Key word: Cashew, Tea Mosquito bug, *Helopetis Antonii* Signoret

Introduction

Cashew, (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) is an important profitable nut crop of India. The nuts, apple and other derivatives of this crop are of commercial importance. Its commercial importance and adaptive ability in a wide range of agro climatic conditions, it has become a crop of high economy and attained the status of an export oriented commodity bringing considerable foreign exchange to the country (Zote *et al.* 2016).

India is the largest processor, consumer and exporter of cashew kernel in the world. But the production of cashew in our country is not sufficient to meet the requirements of industry. Therefore, there is a crucial need to increase the cashew production in our country. On the other hand, this challenge of improving the indigenous production is being challenged with many constraints of various kinds ranging from biotic to abiotic factor. Among the biotic factors, tea mosquito bug alone has a potential to cause 40 to 50 per cent yield loss in cashew (Saroj *et al.*, 2016).

None of the cashew varieties are resistant to this pest, although, some of the accessions show low incidence of the tea mosquito bug (Ambika *et al.*, 1979; Saroj *et al.*, 2016). Further, the pest population density and intensity of incidence varies from tree to tree, some being heavily infested and some are practically free from infestation (Pillai, 1980; Pillai *et al.*, 1984).

Looking to the importance of different components of integrated pest management, resistant cultivars are better among all components, as it is safer to natural enemies and ultimately to the entire ecosystem. With this background, present study aimed to identify the source of resistance by the screening of the available varieties.

Material And Methods

Field experiment was conducted during 2014-15 and 2021-22 at Agriculture Experimental Station, Navsari Agricultural University,

Two-way matrix (Shoots × Panicles) for TMB susceptibility classification.

Shoots/ Panicles	0 to 0.50	0.51 to 1.0 or more
0 to 0.50	Less Susceptible	Susceptible
0.51 to 1.0 or more	Moderately Susceptible	Highly susceptible

Results And Discussion

The pool results of eight year data on shoot damage scale of tea mosquito bug during 2014-15 to 2021-2022 (Table 1) was in the range of 0.17 to 0.44 in different varieties. Vengurla-2 recorded lowest shoot damage scale (0.17) followed by Vengurla-1 (0.19), Vengurla-7 (0.26), Vengurla-6 (0.27), Vengurla-5 (0.36) and Vengurla-4 (0.39). While, Vengurla-3 recorded highest shoot damage scale (0.44).

The pool results of eight year data on panicle damage scale of tea mosquito bug (Table 1) was in the range of 0.29 to 0.65 in different varieties. Vengurla-2 recorded lowest panicle damage scale (0.28) followed by Vengurla-1 (0.29), Vengurla-6 (0.33), Vengurla-7 (0.36), Vengurla-5 and Vengurla-6 (0.49) respectively. While, Vengurla-3 recorded highest panicle damage scale (0.65).

Paria (20°26'39" N, 72°55'58" E, 15 mmsl) to screen out different seven varieties of cashew for their susceptibility to tea mosquito bug. The varieties were evaluated based on damage score.

The amount of damage to the shoots and panicles were recorded on a 0-4 scale on the basis of the number and nature of necrotic lesions (Ambika *et al.*, 1979) as given below:

No damage

1 to 3 necrotic streaks/lesions on the shoot/panicle involving apple and nut

4 to 6 coalescing or non-coalescing lesions/streaks on the shoot/panicle involving apple and nut

Beyond six coalescing or non-coalescing lesions/streaks on the shoot/panicle involving apple and nut

Lesions/streaks confluent or wilting or drying of affected shoot /panicle involving apple and nut

Two trees in each variety were selected for observations. Scoring for tea mosquito bug infestation was done during the regular flushing and flowering season. *i.e.*, October to March. On each tree, an area of 0.5 m × 0.5 m quadrant was marked on four side's viz., East, West, North and South. Observations were recorded on total number of shoots and panicles in each quadrant and the damage score of tea mosquito bug affected shoot and panicle. The mean score per tree was worked out from the total score values of four quadrants divided by the total number of shoots and panicles. The mean score values recorded at fortnightly intervals on shoots and panicles from two sample trees per variety was assessed separately for each year. Three observations were recorded for the shoots and panicles separately during each year. The pooled mean of eight years data were used for comparison.

The varieties were grouped into a two-way matrix, based on their mean damaged scores to shoots and panicles as developed by Beevi and Mahapatro (2007).

The average of shoot and panicle damage scale of tea mosquito bug (Table 1) was in the range of 0.44 to 1.09 in different varieties. Vengurla-2 recorded lowest shoot damage scale (0.44) followed by Vengurla-1 (0.48), Vengurla-6 (0.60), Vengurla-7(0.62), Vengurla-5 (0.85) and Vengurla-4 (0.88). While, Vengurla-3 recorded highest shoot damage scale (1.09). While, Vengurla-3 recorded highest average damage scale (1.09). Based on mean damage scales to shoots and panicles due to tea mosquito bug, varieties Vengurla-2, Vengurla-1, Vengurla-6, Vengurla-7, Vengurla-5 and Vengurla-4 found less susceptible.

Various researchers have screened the different cashew varieties for their reaction to tea mosquito bug and reported that none of the varieties were free from the attack of tea mosquito bug. However,

degree of susceptibility was varying among different varieties (Sathiamma, 1979; Ambika, *et al.*, 1979; Sundararaju, 1999). Thiramalaraju *et al.*, (2002) at Bangalore, Karnataka reported that Vengurla-1 was highly susceptible, whereas Vengurla-3 was least susceptible and Vengurla-2, Vengurla-4 and Vengurla-5 were moderately susceptible. Naik *et al.* (2013) at Bengaluru, Karnataka observed that Vengurla-7 was promising, Vengurla-1 was susceptible

and Vengurla-4 was highly susceptible. Saroj *et al.* (2016) reported that Vengurla-7 and Vengurla-3 were moderately susceptible and Vengurla-4 highly susceptible. According to report of Directorate of Cashew Research, Puttur, Karnataka, Vengurla-4 recorded higher damage scale of 1.38 (Anonymous, 2019). Above report are supports to the present findings.

Pooled (8 year) TMB damage scale in different accessions of cashew. (2014-15 to 2021-22)

Sr. No.	Variety	Pooled TMB Damage Scale		Average of shoot & panicle	Category
		Shoot	Panicles		
1	V1	0.19	0.29	0.48	LS
2	V2	0.17	0.28	0.44	LS
3	V3	0.44	0.65	1.09	S
4	V4	0.39	0.49	0.88	LS
5	V5	0.36	0.49	0.85	LS
6	V6	0.27	0.33	0.60	LS
7	V7	0.26	0.36	0.62	LS

Acknowledgements.

The authors wish to express sincere thanks to Research Scientist of Agriculture Experimental Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Paria, Gujarat, field facilities during research work. Conflict of interest. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. **Ambika, B., Abraham, C. C. and Vidyadharan, K. K. (1979).** Relative susceptibility of cashew types to infestation by *Helopeltis antonii* Signoret (Heteroptera: Miridae). Proceedings of placosym II, India, 513-516.
2. **Anonymous (2019).** Annual Report 2018-2019, ICAR-Directorate of Cashew Research, Puttur, Karnataka, India, pp. 18-19.
3. **Beevi, S. P. and Mahapatro, G. K. (2007).** A new field screening methodology for cashew genotypes against tea mosquito bug, *Helopeltis antonii* Signoret. Journal of Plantation Crops, 35(3): 139-145.
4. **Naik, M. C., Pramod, B. Sasivihally, K., Kalavathi and Chakravarthy, A. K. (2013).** Screening cashew varieties against *Helopeltis antonii* Signoret (Hemiptera: Miridae) in coastal Karnataka, Insect Environment, 19(2): 121-122.
5. **Pillai, G. B. (1980).** Pest problem of cashew. Cashew

Causeri, 2(2): 3-10.

6. **Pillai, G. B., Singh, V., Dubey, O. P. and Abraham, V. A. (1984).** Seasonal abundance of tea mosquito, *Helopeltis antonii* Signoret on cashew in relation to meteorological factors. International Society for Horticultural Sciences, Kerala, India, pp. 103-110.
7. **Saroj, P. L., Bhat, P. S. and Srikumar, K. K. (2016).** Tea mosquito bug (*Helopeltis* spp.)-A devastating pest of cashew plantations in India: A review. Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences, 86(2): 151-162.
8. **Sundararaju, D. (1999).** Screening of cashew accessions to tea mosquito bug, *Helopeltis antonii* Sign. (Heteroptera: Miridae). The Cashew, 13(4):20-26.
9. **Thirumalaraju, G. T. (2002).** Ecology and management of Tea mosquito bug, *Helopeltis antonii* Signoret (Hemiptera: Miridae) on cashew. Ph.D. Thesis, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore, pp. 88-97.
10. **Zote, V. K., Salvi, S. P. and Gajbhiye, R. C. (2016).** Seasonal diversity of insect pests of cashew (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) in west coast of Maharashtra. Pestology, 40(10): 30-33.